

The Numismatic
Chronicle 173
Offprint

Further Imitations of Trajanic Bronze
Coins from Britain

by

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LONDON
THE ROYAL NUMISMATIC SOCIETY
2013

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[PLATES 22-25]

IN VOLUME 170 of this journal, an unusual die-linked group of three imitative sestertii with portraits of Trajan was published (PI. 22, 1–3).² These coins are from two obverse and two reverse dies. One of the latter does not bear an image, but just the typical Trajanic ‘SPQR [OPTI]MO PRINCIPI’ legend and a large SC; the other reverse die shows a garbled, retrograde version of the same legend and a *modius* with stylised grain ears, flanked by the letters S–C: it is probably copied from Nerva’s well-known sestertius type PLEBEI VRBANAE FRUMENTO CONSTITVTO.³ The imitative sestertius featuring the epigraphic reverse type (PI. 22, 1) is a find from Somerset and was reported to the Portable Antiquities Scheme in 2009. The two other coins of the group – struck from the *modius* reverse – are from the coin trade and there is no hard and fast evidence for their provenance. Their present locations, however, can now be specified: both of these sestertii currently reside in private collections in the United States. The first (here PI. 22, 2) is in the collection of Richard Beleson; the second (PI. 22, 3), originally known just from a poor illustration in Frank Kovacs’s FPL 29, no. 57, has recently been located in the collection of Dr Christian Jones.⁴

Of the three coins in the group published in 2010, just one was a documented English site find. Hence, the group’s origin could not be established with certainty, although local production seemed likely.⁵ Fortunately, new evidence has emerged in the meantime.

Sestertius

obv. IMP [CAES NERVAE IPAIANO] AVG GER DAC P M [TR] P C [OS V P P]
Laureate bust of Trajan right, drapery on left shoulder.

¹ Thanks are due to Richard Beleson and Dr Christian Jones for sharing information about sestertii in their collections, to Sam Moorhead and Philippa Walton (London) for directing my attention to two newly found imitative bronzes published in this contribution, and especially to Adrian Marsden (Norwich). He generously sent the important Sparham and Birdlip sestertii discussed below to my Vienna office for the purpose of study and also informed me about the discovery of the ‘Hampshire’ piece. The comments and suggestions provided by an anonymous reader of this journal are gratefully acknowledged. A preliminary version of this paper was presented at the ‘Moneta Britannia’ conference in York on 14 July 2011.

² B.E. Woytek, ‘A new ‘Trajanic’ sestertius from Somerset and its context: some general remarks on struck copies of Imperial bronze coins of Trajan’, *NC* 170 (2010), pp. 115–28.

³ *RIC* 2, Nerva 89 and 103.

⁴ The photograph published here has generously been supplied by the collector.

⁵ Thus Woytek, ‘New ‘Trajanic’ sestertius’, p. 125.

Dotted border.

Die break across the neck.

rev. SDOP OPTIMO PPINDI[PI] (retrograde; legend starting at 4 o'clock)

S – C (in left and right fields)

Rectangular *modius* with seven stylised corn ears/poppies. Exergual line.

Dotted border.

Weight 22.47g, 11h, max. diameter 32.6mm

Found at Sparham in Norfolk in August 2009.

Private collection.

Pl. 22, 4 and 4a

This coin was discovered by Don Mahoney, an American metal detectorist, and was recorded for the Portable Antiquities Scheme later in the year by Adrian Marsden, who notified me of the find. It is an obverse and reverse die duplicate of the sestertius illustrated on **Pl. 22, 2**, currently in the Beleson collection. Beleson's piece was acquired from a Classical Numismatic Group list, which also featured a special 'collection of coins relating to Roman Britain';⁶ this fuels speculation that it is a British find as well.

The new coin is corroded in some spots, but the reverse is well-struck and in particular the stalks sticking out from the *modius* can be discerned quite clearly. Each of them seems to have a knob and a kind of tuft at the end; the die-cutter obviously combined features of the corn-ears and the poppy which are clearly differentiated on regular Roman coins featuring *modii*. The Sparham sestertius brings the total of coins in this imitative group currently known to four. Since two of them have a documented English findspot, we may now confidently ascribe the issue to Roman Britain. The two coins were found in different regions of England, about 200 miles distant from one another as the crow flies. Hence, it is not possible to pin down the production area of the coins on the evidence currently available.

Since few imitations of Trajan sestertii have been recorded in Britain so far, it seems useful to publish here also the three following pieces, kindly communicated to me by British colleagues in the recent past.

Sestertius

obv. IMP CAES NERVAE TRAIANO AVG GER DAC P M T POS V P

Laureate bust of Trajan right, undraped, with strongly curved truncation line.

Dotted border.

rev.]R OPTIMO PRIN[CIPI]

Left field: retrograde S, right field: C

Female figure in long pleated garment seated to the left on throne with high back and pointed legs. She holds a long sceptre in her right hand, leans her left arm on the back of the throne and draws up a fold of drapery with her left hand. Her feet are on a footstool. Exergual line.

Dotted border.

Weight 20.05g, 6h, max. diameter 33.4mm

Found at Birdlip in Gloucestershire in 2011.

Private collection.

Pl. 23, 5 and 5a

⁶ *Classical Numismatic Review* 18, no. 2 (1993), no. 203.

This sestertius, which was recorded by Adrian Marsden, is struck on a broad flan of excellent workmanship. Its die-axis conforms with the alignment observed on all of Trajan's regular imperial issues, viz. 6 o'clock. The coin is of considerable typological interest. It copies a rare Trajanic sestertius type of the COS V-period (AD 103–111), viz. *MIR* 246 (PI. 23, 6–7).⁷ There can be no doubt about the prototype, since the imitation accurately reproduces two of the salient features of its reverse image: the sceptre and the gesture with which the woman lifts the drapery at her left shoulder. The most important change, as compared to the prototype, concerns the letters SC, which were shifted from the exergue into the field, with the S being retrograde. As the lower part of the reverse is somewhat weakly struck, it is difficult to be sure whether the globe at the feet of the personification was copied too, but it may well be the case.⁸ Although Henri Cohen and Paul Strack called the divinity in this reverse type 'Providence?'⁹ and 'Securitas'¹⁰ respectively, Franziska Schmidt-Dick has recently pointed out that she must in fact be 'Ops', since the same reverse type is labelled OPI AVG on a sestertius of Antoninus Pius (PI. 23, 8).¹¹ The retrograde S on the reverse of the Birdlip coin recalls the retrograde reverse legend on the *modius* sestertii discussed above; in general, retrograde legends are not that common on Trajanic copies.¹² Nevertheless, the Birdlip sestertius does not seem to share a common origin with the *modius* group. Its powerful, yet highly stylised emperor portrait is not directly related to the bust on the two obverse dies hitherto attested for the *modius* sestertii. If the Birdlip sestertius was produced locally – which is likely –, this would provide evidence for the presence of the rare prototype *MIR* 246 in Britain. Of the ten specimens of the Trajanic original presently known, just one can be provenanced: it was found in controlled excavation of the auxiliary fort in Carnuntum (*Pannonia superior*: PI. 23, 6).¹³

Sestertius

obv. [IM]P CAES NERV[AE] TRAIANO AVG GER DA[

Laureate bust of Trajan right, with drapery on the left shoulder (visible at the front).

rev. SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI

S C (beneath design)

Single-span bridge with tower at each end. Indication of waterline? (This is unclear due to the coin's fragmented state.)

⁷ B. Woytek, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117)*. *Moneta Imperii Romani* 14. 2 vols (Vienna, 2010) [= *MIR Traianus*], 246 (10 specimens cited; approximate date: AD 106–107) = P.L. Strack, *Untersuchungen zur römischen Reichsprägung des zweiten Jahrhunderts. Teil I: Die Reichsprägung zur Zeit des Traian* (Stuttgart, 1931), 402; cp. *RIC* 2, Trajan 514, 517 and 518.

⁸ No specimen of this type with an undraped bust on the obverse is listed in *MIR*. It is attested with *MIR* busts b (r., with drapery on far shoulder), c (r., with aegis), f (r., draped and cuirassed, seen from behind) and p (l., with aegis).

⁹ Evidently on account of the globe at her feet: H. Cohen, *Description historique des monnaies frappées sous l'Empire Romain communément appelées médailles impériales*, vol. 2 (Paris – London 1882), p. 67, no. 489.

¹⁰ Presumably in view of the transverse sceptre and the position of the left arm: Strack, *Reichsprägung*, pp. 170f.

¹¹ See F. Schmidt-Dick, *Typenatlas der römischen Reichsprägung von Augustus bis Aemilianus*. Vol. 1: *Weibliche Darstellungen* (Vienna, 2002), p. 81, Ops f5A/04; *BMCRE* 4, Antoninus Pius 1258.

¹² See Woytek, 'New 'Trajanic' Sestertius', p. 124.

¹³ See *MIR Traianus* p. 315, listed under no. 246c.

Dotted border.

Fragmented.

Weight 14.71g, 12h, max. diameter 31.6mm

Discovered on the Isle of Wight on 1 May 2013.

Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS), find no. IOW-2C6A13

Private collection.

Pl. 24, 9 and 9a

This coin – kindly brought to my attention by Sam Moorhead – copies one of Trajan’s best-known types of bronze coins (see **Pl. 24, 10**).¹⁴ Ironically, it is also one of the most controversial ones, since the identification of the bridge depicted here continues to divide scholarly opinion. To some extent, this uncertainty is paralleled by the doubts surrounding a bridge figured on the reverse of small anonymous bronze coins of the Constantinian period showing a bust of the Genius populi Romani on the obverse.¹⁵ Both coin types have been thought to depict the respective bridges built by Trajan and Constantine the Great over the Danube,¹⁶ but in both cases this seems to be the least likely identification.¹⁷ Whatever the precise background of the reverse image may be, this is the first imitative coin of this type recorded by the present writer.¹⁸ Although the overall style of the new coin is appealing and the ‘two-tier’ structure of the bridge is copied faithfully, several details have been changed, as compared to the prototype. The trophies and statues surmounting the entrances of the bridge on the original are not clear on the imitation. More importantly, the barge moored near the right bank seems to have been left out, and the SC was moved from below the waterline to the space immediately beneath the bridge.

Sestertius

obv. IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM [

Laureate bust of Trajan right, with drapery on the left shoulder (visible at the front and at the back); at the front, round *fibula*.

rev. TR P[

¹⁴ *MIR Traianus* 314–6 (sestertius, dupondius, as) = Strack, *Reichsprägung* 385; cp. *RIC* 2, Trajan 569f. 157 specimens of the sestertii cited in *MIR*; approximate date: AD 107–110.

¹⁵ *RIC* 8, Constantinople 21 (AD 330). This bridge has two towers like the Trajanic one, but it is straight and rests on two supports.

¹⁶ In the case of Trajan’s bronzes, this is the traditional hypothesis, put forward by Sebastiano Erizzo (1525–1585) and defended against critics already by R. Fabretti, *De columna Traiani syntagma* (Rome, 1690), pp. 98 and 301–6. This view was also shared by Strack, *Reichsprägung* pp. 127–9, recently followed by C.L. Clay, ‘The Roman Imperial coinage of Trajan’, *NC* 172 (2012), pp. 347–62, at p. 358.

¹⁷ On the problem of the Constantinian bridge, see most recently L. Ramskold, ‘Coins and medallions struck for the inauguration of Constantinopolis 11 May 330’ in M. Rakocija (ed.), *The Days of St. Emperor Constantine and Helena. Niš and Byzantium. Ninth Symposium. Niš, 3–5 June 2010* (Niš, 2011), pp. 125–57, esp. 136–8 (with convincing arguments against the interpretation as the bridge over the Danube). P.V. Hill, *The Monuments of Ancient Rome as Coin Types* (London, 1989), pp. 105f. argued that Trajan’s coins cannot represent the bridge over the Danube, but perhaps depict the Pons Sublicius in Rome. See also the treatment in Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, pp. 128–30.

¹⁸ Two strange-looking sestertii of this type from the same pair of dies are perhaps not ancient imitations, but rather modern forgeries: The New York Sale (Baldwin’s – Markov – M&M) 7 (15 January 2004), no. 249 (23.72g); Stack’s Coin Galleries, 20 October 2010, no. 197 (29.43g). I am grateful to Markus Peter (Basle) for discussing these problematic coins with me.

S C (in exergue)

Pax, draped, seated left on throne, holding olive branch in extended right hand and resting left arm on the throne's back.

Exergual line.

Weight 17.10g, 5/6h

Bought from a detectorist or dealer in Hampshire.

Private collection.

Pl. 24, 11

Unlike the sestertii presented above, this coin was purchased in trade; Adrian Marsden did not record it immediately after discovery, but from the collection where it currently resides. Still, according to information provided by the collector, the piece is almost certainly a metal detector find from the south of England. It features the most common sestertius reverse of the early period of Trajan's rule, Pax seated to the left. Though the consular number on the reverse cannot be read, the sestertius type it copies must have been issued in the period AD 98–102 (see, e.g., **Pl. 24, 12**).¹⁹ As compared to the model, the transverse sceptre held by Pax is missing on the copy; yet, the absence of a *cornucopiae* and an altar assure us that a Pax sestertius was imitated here, not a piece with a Concordia reverse.

In general, imitative middle bronzes with Trajanic types are encountered more frequently than imitations of sestertii of Trajan, as has been discussed in greater detail elsewhere.²⁰ The denominational differentiation between dupondii and asses probably did not matter much to the workers responsible for the production of irregular issues. Evidence for this is provided by cases in which the imitations are typological hybrids between the two denominations, such as the excellently preserved coin at **Pl. 25, 13 and 13a**, from the French trade.²¹ This piece, struck on a thinnish flan, combines an obverse showing the laureate head of the emperor with a wonderfully detailed Dacian trophy on the reverse,²² a type that on official bronze coins is exclusive to dupondii (cp. **Pl. 25, 14**). The final coin in this survey, however, is an imitative middle bronze whose obverse and reverse types are correctly paired, namely a copy of a common Trajanic dupondius type minted in AD 100 (**Pl. 25, 16**),²³ which was discovered on 21 October 2010 in Therfield, Hertfordshire.

Dupondius

obv.]S NERVA TRAIAN AVG GE[

Head of Trajan right, radiate crown sketchily indicated.

rev. TR PO[?] – [?]IOS III PP

SC (in exergue)

Abundantia-Securitas seated left on crossed *cornucopiae*, placing feet on stool, holding short sceptre in the right hand.

Exergual line, on the left side with short vertical strokes.

¹⁹ The possible prototypes are *MIR Traianus* nos 16, 27 and 58 (cos II); 76 and 93[H] (cos III); 107 (cos IIII).

²⁰ Cp. Woytek, 'New 'Trajanic' Sestertius', pp. 126f.

²¹ Comptoir Général Financier, *Monnaies* 43 (29 April 2010), no. 417.

²² The legends are impeccable as to their content; they copy the standard inscriptions of Trajan's COS V bronzes. The shape of the letter Q in the reverse legend is, however, irregular.

²³ *MIR Traianus* 67 = Strack, *Reichsprägung* 328 = *RIC* 2, Trajan 411.

Weight 9.90g, axis 8h, max. diameter 27.3mm

On the obverse, a small cut across the emperor's head; on the reverse, several scratches.
Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS), find no. BH-9EEE11

Pl. 25, 15

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- 1 Imitative sestertius. *NC* 2010, pl. 7, no. 1 and 1a. PAS SOM-E7EDD7.
- 2 Imitative sestertius. *NC* 2010, pl. 7, no. 2 and 2a. Richard Beleson collection. Photo © Frank Kovacs.
- 3 Imitative sestertius. *NC* 2010, pl. 7, no. 3. Dr Christian Jones collection (26.89g, 6h, max. diameter 33mm). Photo © Dr Christian Jones.
- 4 Imitative sestertius, found at Sparham. From the same dies as coin 2. Private collection (22.47g, 11h). Photo author.
- 4a No. 4, enlarged.
- 5 Imitative sestertius copying *MIR Traianus* 246. Found at Birdlip. Private collection (20.05g, 6h). Photo author.
- 5a No. 5, enlarged.
- 6 Sestertius, *MIR Traianus* 246c. Found at the auxiliary fort in Carnuntum, 1993 excavation campaign; inv. no. 25.281 (26.48g, 6h). Photo Austrian Academy of Sciences.
- 7 Sestertius, *MIR Traianus* 246c. Italo Vecchi 14 (5 February 1999), no. 1100 (24.84g). Photo © Italo Vecchi.
- 8 Antoninus Pius, sestertius, *BMCRE* 4, Antoninus Pius 1258. *Numismatica Ars Classica* 64 (17 May 2012), no. 1182 (28.38g, 34mm). Photo © NAC.
- 9 Imitative sestertius copying *MIR Traianus* 314b. Found on the Isle of Wight. Private collection. PAS IOW-2C6A13.
- 9a No. 9, enlarged.
- 10 Sestertius, *MIR Traianus* 314b. Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Preussischer Kulturbesitz, Münzkabinett (24.94g, 6h). Photo author.
- 11 Imitative sestertius, copying a Trajanic type with a Pax reverse. Private collection (17.10g, 5/6h). Photo © Adrian Marsden.
- 12 Sestertius, *MIR Traianus* 107b. *Münzen und Medaillen AG List* 420 (March 1980), no. 29. Photo © MMAG.
- 13 Imitative middle bronze; reverse copying *MIR Traianus* 196. *Comptoir Général Financier, Monnaies* 43 (29 April 2010), no. 417 (5.84g, 6h, 24mm). Photo © CGF.
- 13a No. 13, enlarged.
- 14 Dupondius, *MIR Traianus* 196b. *Numismatica Ars Classica* 25 (25 June 2003), no. 444 (12.59g, 28mm). Photo © NAC.
- 15 Imitative dupondius copying *MIR Traianus* 67a. Found at Therfield. PAS BH-9EEE11.
- 16 Dupondius, *MIR Traianus* 67a. *Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna*, inv. MK 8206 (13.74g, 6h). Photo author.

PLATE 22

WOYTEK, FURTHER IMITATIONS OF TRAJANIC BRONZE COINS FROM BRITAIN (1)

WOYTEK, FURTHER IMITATIONS OF TRAJANIC BRONZE COINS FROM BRITAIN (2)

PLATE 24

WOYTEK, FURTHER IMITATIONS OF TRAJANIC BRONZE COINS FROM BRITAIN (3)

13a

13

14

15

16

